

DOI: 10.31866/2617-2674.5.2.2022.269542

PHOTO ART PROJECT
IN SEARCH OF THE MEANING OF BEING

Oleksandr Bezruchko^{1a}, Valeriia Hrymalska^{2a}

¹ Doctor of Study of Art, PhD in Cinematographic Art, Television, Professor;
e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388

² Master of Audiovisual Arts and Productions;
e-mail: valeriia hrymalska@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0002-5823-7321

^a Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv, Ukraine

ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ
«В ПОШУКАХ СЕНСУ БУТТЯ»

Олександр Безручко^{1а}, Валерія Гримальська^{2а}

¹ доктор мистецтвознавства, професор;
e-mail: oleksandr_bezruchko@ukr.net; ORCID: 0000-0001-8360-9388

² магістр аудіовізуального мистецтва та виробництва;
e-mail: valeriia hrymalska@gmail.com; ORCID: 0000-0002-5823-7321

^a Київський національний університет культури і мистецтв, Київ, Україна

The author's idea for this photography art project is to capture the important aspects of human life that give our lives meaning, such as family, friendship, and love. The aim is to show sincere emotions, people's relationships with each other, with the world around them and with themselves. Before, the author tried not just to photograph moments in the lives of the people around her, but in each photograph to tell a story – theirs and her own.

The series consists of both staged and unstaged photographs in a cinematic style. The order in which the photographs are placed in the photo art project, their titles, and the color correction in post-production illustrate the changes in the state of mind of the storyteller herself. Throughout the project, the journey from hopelessness to a newfound meaning of life is illustrated through the search for important life values and beauty in the surrounding world, people, and their relationships.

Photo No. 1

**"Lost" from the Photo Art Project
In Search of the Meaning of Being**

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 6D /
Sigma 35mm f/1.4

Settings:
35 mm | F2.2 | ISO 200 | 1/500 s

**Image No. 1 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves

Light scheme
Natural. The photo was taken
in daylight at 7:15 PM.

The author's idea of photograph No. 1. The photograph "Lost" depicts the protagonist of the photographic art project. She is a reflection of the narrator herself and will appear throughout the project to illustrate the author's journey from disillusionment with her work, to regaining faith in herself and her possibilities.

The photograph "Lost" illustrates this very feeling of loss and disillusionment, when there is no inspiration, no ideas, and no desire to do anything. However, the beam of light illuminating the heroine's face symbolizes hope and guides the girl to begin her journey toward self-realization.

Photo No. 2

**"Frustration": from the Photo Art Project
In Search of the Meaning of Being**

Camera / Lens

Panasonic Lumix DMC-LX100 /
Leica 24-75mm lens

Settings:

75 mm | F5 | ISO 200 | 1/500 s

**Image No. 2 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves

Light scheme

Natural light. The photo was taken
in daylight at 6:23 pm.

The author's idea of photograph No. 2. Photography No. 2 illustrates a period when one refuses to devote time to one's interests and new hobbies, doubting one's success. In such moments, days pass meaninglessly. But it is important to know that success comes with time and work, so don't be afraid to fail, but keep doing what you enjoy and gradually get pleasure in what you do.

To illustrate this feeling, the heroine is depicted sitting frustratedly in front of her laptop screen while life passes by.

Photo No. 3

**"Dead End" from the Photo Art Project
In Search of the Meaning of Being**

Camera / Lens

Panasonic Lumix DMC-LX100 /
Leica 24-75mm

Settings:

75 mm | F11 | ISO 1600 | 1/100 s

**Image No. 3 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves
- Adding elements using a stamp tool
- Removing unnecessary elements with
a stamp tool

Light scheme

Natural light. The photo was taken
in daylight at 6:23 pm.

The author's idea of photograph No. 3. Photo №3 illustrates the moment when a person is disappointed in everything, he gives up and does not see the future. At this point, you need to realize that you need to change direction, turn around, and not look for a way out where there is none.

Photo No. 4

232

**"Contemplating the Beautiful" from the Photo Art Project
In Search of the Meaning of Being**

Camera / Lens
Canon EOS 6D /
Capon 70-200mm f/4

Settings:
109 mm | F4 | ISO 800 | 1/1000 s

**Image No. 4 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves
- Removing unnecessary elements with
a stamp tool

Light scheme
Natural light. The photo was taken
in daylight at 3:10 pm.

The author's idea of photograph No. 4. The following photos in the photography project reflect positive human emotions, as well as important aspects of human life that give our lives meaning, such as family, friendship, and love.

The main character, like the author of this project, is now focused on contemplating the happy and intimate moments of human relationships, hoping to be inspired by these moments and tell a story in each photo.

Photo No. 5

234

**"The Flow of Time 2": from the Photo Art Project
In Search of the Meaning of Being**

Camera / Lens

Panasonic Lumix DMC-LX100 /
Leica 24-75mm

Settings:

70 mm | F2.8 | ISO 200 | 1/2000 s

**Image No. 5 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves
- Removing unnecessary elements with
a stamp tool

Light scheme

Natural light. The photo was taken
in daylight at 3:10 pm.

The author's idea of photograph No. 5. In this photograph, the past looks lovingly toward the future. The warmth of the mood is emphasized by the sunlight that illuminates all the characters in the photograph and embodies hope.

Photo No. 6

“Unique connection” from the Photo Art Project
In Search of the Meaning of Being

Camera / Lens

Panasonic Lumix DMC-LX100 /
Leica 24-75mm

Settings:

75 mm | F4.5 | ISO 200 | 1/1300 s

**Image No. 6 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves
- Removing unnecessary elements with
a stamp tool

Light scheme

Natural light. The photo was taken
in daylight at 6:30 pm.

The author's idea of photograph No. 6. In continuation of the idea of the series of photographs "Unique connection", the connection between sisters is illustrated here. Childhood moments of sibling bonding are unrepeatable moments that form the foundation of your personality.

Photo No. 7

**“The Sky We Walk Under” from the Photo Art Project
In Search of the Meaning of Being**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 300V / Sigma 35mm 1.4
Kodak Color Plus 200 ISO film.
C-41 film development process, scanning
on a Fujifilm Frontier SP-3000 scanner.

Settings:

35 mm | Aperture auto |
ISO 200 | Shutter speed auto

**Image No. 7 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves
- Removing unnecessary elements with
a stamp tool

Light scheme

Natural light. The photo was taken
in daylight at 5:10 pm.

The author's idea of photograph No. 7. This photo symbolizes the unexpected meeting of different worlds: the old European one, symbolizing Vienna's Belvedere, and the group of Chinese dancers performing their folk dance in front of it.

Do not be afraid to experiment in your work with different, dissimilar styles, in an attempt to find your own.

And the vast and beautiful sky symbolizes the endless freedom of creativity. Under this sky, creating unique things, many diverse people find their calling.

Photo No. 8

"Love" from the Photo Art Project
In search of the meaning of being

Camera / Lens

Panasonic Lumix DMC-LX100 /
Leica 24-75mm

Settings:

35 mm | F1.7 | ISO 1600 | 1/50 s

**Image No. 8 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves

Light scheme

Artificial. Incandescent bulb.
The color temperature is roughly 2700 K.

The author's idea of photograph No. 8. There is no more beautiful feeling when you know that there is a person in the world who will always support you and perceive you as you are.

Photo No. 9

**"Among people" from the Photo Art Project
In search of the meaning of being**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 300V / Sigma 35mm 1.4
Kodak Color Plus 200 ISO film.
C-41 film development process, scanning
on a Fujifilm Frontier SP-3000 scanner.

Settings:

35 mm | Aperture auto |
ISO 200 | Shutter speed auto

**Image No. 8 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves

Light scheme

Artificial. Incandescent lamp.
The color temperature is roughly 2700 K.

The author's idea of photograph No. 9. Another important aspect of human life is socialization with the world around us. It is meetings with friends and new people, visiting new locations, inspiring creativity, and promoting personal development.

Photo No. 10

**"Touching Hope" from the Photo Art Project
In search of the meaning of being**

Camera / Lens

Canon EOS 6D /
Capon 70-200 mm f/4

Settings:

35 mm | F1.4 | ISO 100 | 1/2500 s

**Image No. 8 editing with
Adobe Photoshop:**

- Cropping
- Editing exposure, shadows,
and contrast in curves
- Color editing in curves
- Removing unnecessary elements with
a stamp tool

Light scheme

Natural light. The photo was taken
in daylight at 6:20 pm.

The author's idea of photograph No. 10. Throughout the photo project the journey from hopelessness to a newfound meaning of life is shown, through the search for important life values and beauty in the surrounding world, people, and their relationships.

As stated in the first photo of this project, the main character is a reflection of the author herself and illustrates the author's journey from disillusionment in her work to finding faith in herself and her possibilities.

By observing the important aspects of human life that give our lives meaning, such as family, friendship, and love, the heroine has come a long way, until she found hope and faith.

Hope is something that cannot be shown but can be felt. That is why hope is not visualized in the picture, but the light and movement of the heroine's gesture are what symbolize it.

